

Power Quality Enhancement in Solar-Wind Integrated Grid for Bidirectional EV Charging Using Conjugate Gradient Controller

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KEYWORDS

Bidirectional EV Charging, Conjugate Gradient Controller, Power Quality Enhancement, Solar-Wind Hybrid System, Grid Integration, Voltage Source Converter (VSC), Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)

ABSTRACT

The growing adoption of plug-in electric vehicles (EVs) has accelerated the demand for reliable and efficient charging infrastructure that ensures stable grid performance. In this context, renewable energy sources such as solar and wind play a crucial role in supporting clean energy supply for EV charging. This paper proposes a grid-connected bidirectional EV charging system integrated with both solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy sources. Unlike conventional systems, the proposed architecture emphasizes the contribution of wind power in enhancing overall grid power quality, especially under varying load and generation conditions. The energy from solar and wind is transferred to the grid via a bidirectional voltage source converter (VSC), which manages both active power flow and power quality regulation. To ensure continuous distortion-free operation and compliance with IEEE-519 standards, a Conjugate Gradient Controller (CGC) is implemented for adaptive control of the VSC. The controller effectively improves total system stability, maintains voltage and current profiles, and significantly reduces total harmonic distortion (THD) levels under dynamic conditions. The performance of the proposed system is validated through detailed MATLAB/Simulink simulations, demonstrating its effectiveness in providing stable and high-quality EV charging within a renewable-integrated grid framework.

I. Introduction

The rapid adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) across the globe has placed significant new demands on power distribution systems, especially at the local level. As the number of EV charging loads continues to rise, the grid increasingly struggles to supply pure sinusoidal voltage and current profiles during both charging (G2V) and discharging (V2G) operations [1]. The conventional EV charging infrastructure is often dependent on fossil-fuel-based power sources or non-optimized renewable setups, which undermines the environmental benefits of EVs. For EVs to serve as a truly sustainable transportation solution, the electricity used for their charging must come from renewable energy sources (RES) such as solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy systems [2]. Integrating solar and wind energy into the EV charging network brings several benefits, including enhanced grid efficiency, reduced power losses, increased flexibility, and decreased environmental pollution [3]. However, the variability and intermittency of solar irradiance and wind speed introduce dynamic challenges, such as voltage fluctuations, frequency deviations, and harmonic distortions. These effects are especially pronounced when large-scale EV chargers are connected to the grid simultaneously [4]. Among various RES options, solar PV systems are particularly attractive due to their cost-effectiveness, ease of deployment, and low maintenance [5][6]. Similarly, wind energy can complement solar generation, especially during nighttime or low irradiance periods, forming a hybrid power supply solution [7]. To enhance system performance, researchers have proposed grid-connected charging architectures where bidirectional power flow allows the vehicle battery to discharge energy back to the grid in V2G mode. This bidirectional functionality supports ancillary grid services such as load leveling, voltage support, and harmonic compensation [8][9]. Voltage Source Converters (VSCs) play a crucial role in this context, serving as the interface between the grid, the renewable sources, and the EV battery. They are responsible for active power transfer, voltage regulation, reactive power compensation, and harmonic filtering [10]. While traditional control techniques such as Proportional-Integral (PI) controllers have been commonly used in VSCs, they exhibit limited performance under dynamic conditions and nonlinear

loads [11][12]. More advanced control strategies, such as Model Predictive Control, Sliding Mode Control, and Fuzzy Logic-based methods, have been introduced to address these limitations [13][14]. Nevertheless, these techniques often come with trade-offs in terms of computational complexity, tuning difficulties, or limited real-time adaptability. Notably, many of these approaches fall short in maintaining power quality during adverse weather conditions like overcast or rainy days when solar PV input is unavailable [15][16]. In recent literature, Conjugate Gradient (CG) based adaptive control methods have emerged as promising alternatives due to their fast convergence, low memory requirements, and excellent adaptability in dynamically changing grid environments [17]. The CG algorithm offers improved performance over Least Mean Square (LMS) and Recursive Least Squares (RLS) methods by eliminating the need for matrix inversion and providing faster convergence without the high memory demand of LMF-type algorithms [18][19]. This makes CG controllers highly suitable for real-time applications in smart grid environments, particularly for generating accurate reference current signals for power quality conditioning in VSC-based systems. This paper presents a Conjugate Gradient Controller (CGC)-based bidirectional EV charging system integrated with hybrid renewable energy sources specifically, solar PV and wind energy. The proposed system addresses both G2V and V2G modes under a variety of dynamic and challenging conditions [20]. Unlike conventional systems where the PV is directly tied to the DC bus, the proposed architecture connects the PV and wind systems to the AC side through the VSC. This configuration enables harmonic-free EV charging even during low PV generation conditions such as night or rainy profiles. The CG controller adaptively regulates the VSC to improve power quality, ensuring sinusoidal grid current and voltage waveforms, reduced Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), and compliance with IEEE-519 standards.

Key contributions of this work include:

- The design and implementation of a CG-based adaptive controller for reference current signal generation for the active power filter (PV-APF) embedded in the VSC.

- A dynamic switching logic based on Multi-Step Constant Current (MSCC) technique for smooth transition between G2V and V2G modes.
- A grid-friendly EV charger that ensures harmonic-free battery charging and discharging under all solar and wind availability scenarios.
- Extensive simulation of the proposed system using MATLAB/Simulink under various dynamic load and generation profiles to validate performance improvements in power quality and system stability.

II. System Configuration

The proposed system integrates solar photovoltaic and wind energy sources into a grid-connected bidirectional electric vehicle charging setup as shown in Fig.1. Solar energy is harnessed using a photovoltaic array, while wind energy is captured through a turbine coupled with

a permanent magnet synchronous generator. Both sources are connected to a common DC link through dedicated DC-DC converters, which regulate their outputs and apply maximum power point tracking for efficient energy extraction. A bidirectional voltage source converter interfaces the DC link with the AC grid and the electric vehicle battery. This converter manages energy flow in both grid to vehicle and vehicle to grid modes and also performs active power filtering to improve power quality. A conjugate gradient controller is employed to generate reference signals for the converter, enabling precise compensation of harmonics and reactive power. This ensures voltage and current quality in compliance with grid standards under dynamic conditions. The system is modeled and simulated in MATLAB to evaluate its performance in maintaining stable, distortion-free operation across various renewable generation and load scenarios.

Fig. 1. System configuration.

III. Modeling and Designing of Renewable energy configuration

A. Solar PV System

The solar configuration in the proposed hybrid microgrid consists of a photovoltaic array arranged in a series-parallel structure to achieve the desired voltage and current levels. The photovoltaic system is connected to the DC bus through a DC-DC boost converter that steps up the voltage and regulates the output as shown in Fig.2. To maximize the energy harvested from the

solar panels under varying irradiance and temperature conditions, a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is employed, typically using the incremental conductance method as shown in Fig.4. The converter operates efficiently to track the maximum power point and supply a stable DC voltage to the bus. This stabilized DC output is then available for powering DC loads directly, charging the energy storage system, or being inverted and supplied to AC loads through the grid-connected converter. The solar subsystem plays a critical role in supporting the energy demands of the

microgrid, particularly during daytime operation, while also contributing to overall system stability and sustainability.

Fig. 2 solar PV INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

The modeling and designing of the solar photovoltaic (PV) system involve selecting appropriate modules, configuring series and parallel connections, and integrating a DC-DC converter with MPPT to ensure optimal energy harvesting. Each PV module is modeled using the single-diode equivalent circuit as shown in Fig.3, where the output current is:

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{nkT}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Here, I_{ph} is the photocurrent, I_0 is the reverse saturation current, R_s and R_{sh} are the series and shunt resistances respectively, V is the terminal voltage, n is the ideality factor, T is the cell temperature in Kelvin, and q and K are the electronic charge and Boltzmann constant. The total power output is:

$$P_{PV} = V_{PV} \cdot I_{PV} \quad (2)$$

To match the DC bus voltage, a boost converter is designed with the transfer function:

$$V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (3)$$

Where D is the duty cycle, The MPPT controller, typically an Incremental Conductance algorithm, is applied to track the maximum power point by adjusting the duty cycle in response to changes in solar irradiance G and temperature T as shown in Fig.4. The converter is designed to operate in Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM), and its inductor L and capacitor C values are selected based on:

$$L = \frac{V_{in}(V_{out}-V_{in})}{\Delta I \cdot f_s \cdot V_{out}} \quad (4)$$

$$C = \frac{I_{out} \cdot D}{\Delta V \cdot f_s} \quad (5)$$

Where ΔI is the desired ripple in inductor current, ΔV is the ripple in output voltage, and f_s is the switching frequency. The output of the converter connects to the DC bus, supplying both DC loads and feeding into the grid through an inverter when needed. This model ensures optimal PV performance across varying environmental conditions.

Fig. 4. Flow chat of modified incremental conductance maximum power point algorithm

B. Wind Energy System Configuration using PMSG

In this configuration, a wind turbine is mechanically coupled to a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG). The electrical output of the PMSG is a variable-frequency AC that is first rectified to DC and then converted back to AC through a Voltage Source

Inverter (VSI) for AC load/grid interface or directly supplied to the DC bus of the microgrid.

1. Wind Turbine Power Output:

The mechanical power extracted from wind is given by:

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^3 \cdot C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (6)$$

Where: ρ = Air density (kg / m^3), $A = \pi R^2$ swept area of turbine blades, v = wind speed (m/s), C_p = power coefficient (function of tip speed ratio λ and pitch angle β)

2. Tip Speed Ratio λ :

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega_t R}{v} \quad (7)$$

Where: ω_t : Turbine angular speed (rad/s), R : Blade radius (m)

3. PMSG Modeling (dq-axis):

PMSG electrical dynamics in dq-frame:

$$V_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\psi_d}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_q \quad (8)$$

$$V_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\psi_q}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_d \quad (9)$$

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} P (\psi_d i_q - \psi_q i_d) \quad (10)$$

Where: R_s : Stator resistance, ψ_d, ψ_q : d and q-axis flux linkages, ω_e : Electrical angular speed, T_e : Electromagnetic torque, P : Number of pole pairs

4. Control on the Machine Side

The machine-side control relies heavily on wind speed reference generation in order to get the most power out of the wind turbine. Figure 5 shows the control circuit of an active rectifier-connected PMSG. The ideal ratio of tip speed to actual wind speed is used to determine the reference rotor speed. This is the reference speed:

$$\omega_m^{opt} = \frac{\lambda'_{opt} v_w}{R} \quad (11)$$

The speed of the reference rotor is represented by ω_m^{opt} . The PI speed controller is used to limit the speed error, which is calculated from the ideal wind speed and the actual speed of the PMSG, as reference electromagnetic torque. This means:

$$\omega_r^{error} = \omega_m^{opt} - \omega_r \quad (12)$$

$$T_e^* = k_{p,s}(\omega_r^{error}) + k_{i,s} \int (\omega_r^{error}) dt \quad (13)$$

The variables ω_r^{error} , T_e^* , $k_{p,s}$, and $k_{i,s}$ denote the rotor speed error, reference electromagnetic torque, proportional gain, and integral gain, respectively, of the speed controller.

The reference q-axis current (i_{qm}^*) is:

$$i_{qm}^* = \frac{4T_e^*}{3P} \quad (14)$$

An inner loop current controller regulates the machine side converter, which in turn generates the reference voltage. The coordinates on the d-q axis are:

$$v_{dm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) dt - \omega_e L_s i_{qs} \quad (15)$$

$$v_{qm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{qm}^* - i_{qs}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{qm}^* - i_{qs}) dt + \omega_e (L_s i_{ds} + \lambda_m) \quad (16)$$

The variables v_{dm}^* and v_{qm}^* on the d-q axis represent the reference machine voltage, i_{dm}^* and i_{qm}^* on the d-q axis represent the reference stator current, and the variables $k_{p,mc}$ and $k_{i,mc}$ represent the component gains of the machine current controller, respectively.

The voltage references on the d-q axis are converted into three-phase machine voltage references via inverse park transformation so that the wind turbine can produce its maximum output. Pulse width modulation (PWM) generators use these three-phase machine voltage references and use them to operate the active rectifier on the machine side.

Fig.5 Wind conversion controller

IV. Design of Active Power Filter Control Algorithm for Solar and Wind Integrated System

The Conjugate Gradient Algorithm (CGA)-based Active Power Filter (APF) control algorithm is integrated into a solar and wind hybrid system to enhance power quality by compensating harmonics, managing reactive power,

and balancing load currents in the presence of fluctuating renewable energy sources, as illustrated in Fig.6. This system supplies power to both electric vehicle (EV) charging units and domestic loads, where power quality is often degraded due to the intermittent nature of renewables and EV loads. In this control approach, the Hysteresis Current Controller is employed to regulate the APF. The HCC continuously monitors the error between the actual source currents and the reference current templates generated by the CGA. It maintains this error within a pre-defined hysteresis band and produces the corresponding switching pulses for the Voltage Source Converter (VSC). This method enables fast and accurate current tracking with high dynamic performance. The reference currents are generated adaptively using the Conjugate Gradient Algorithm, which uses measured grid voltages and currents to compute normalized voltage vectors and generate unit current templates. The active and reactive power components are separated, and their associated current vectors are iteratively optimized using the conjugate gradient method to minimize the deviation from ideal current profiles. A DC-DC converter connects the photovoltaic and wind sources to a common DC-link,

with energy management handled by a Modified State of Charge-based Control (MSCC) strategy. This ensures efficient charging of EVs and supply to domestic loads, even under varying renewable input conditions. The combined HCC and CGA strategy effectively filters harmonics, compensates for reactive power, and manages load imbalances. It provides fast transient response, robust control under EV loads, and adaptive performance in the face of renewable energy variability, making it highly suitable for modern distributed power systems with high renewable penetration as shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 6 Grid and wind connected voltage source converter for APF operation

Fig. 7. Conjugate gradient algorithm

This equation generates six unit template signals $z_{pa}, z_{qa}, z_{pb}, z_{qb}, z_{pc}, z_{qc}$ for three-phase voltage signals. These are normalized using the total voltage magnitude v_t to define the direction of active and reactive components in each phase. These templates are later used to estimate the reference currents in active and reactive components.

$$\begin{bmatrix} z_{pa} \\ z_{qa} \\ z_{pb} \\ z_{qb} \\ z_{pc} \\ z_{qc} \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}v_t} \begin{bmatrix} -2\sqrt{3} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & -2 \\ 0 & -2\sqrt{3} & 0 \\ 3 & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -2\sqrt{3} \\ 3 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{sa} \\ v_{sb} \\ v_{sc} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

This computes the average RMS (Root Mean Square) of the line voltages in the system. The total voltage v_t is essential for normalizing phase voltages while

generating the unit vectors in Equation (16), ensuring balanced reference generation across the phases.

$$V_t = \sqrt{\frac{v_{ab}^2 + v_{bc}^2 + v_{ca}^2}{3}} \quad (18)$$

The working operation of the Conjugate Gradient Algorithm (CGA) controller begins by estimating the current tracking error in each phase. Equation (19) is computes the error between the actual phase current $i_{la}(i+1)$ and the estimated component $z_{pa}(i+1) \cdot h_{pa}(i)$, which reflects the output of the adaptive model. This estimation error helps determine how much the current model deviates from the actual signal. Equation (20) is calculates the adaptive step size, denoted as $\beta_{pa}(i)$, which is crucial in defining the direction and rate of convergence of the algorithm. It takes into account the system dynamics and error feedback to intelligently adjust the control response. Equation (21) is updates the active weight vector h_{pa} , which represents the controller's learned behavior or adaptive gain for phase "a". This update is done by moving in the direction of the search vector $q_{pa}(i)$, scaled by the computed step size $\beta_{pa}(i)$, allowing the controller to minimize the error over time. This iterative process enhances the CGA controller's ability to generate accurate reference signals for grid current, ensuring effective compensation of harmonics and stable power delivery.

1. Estimation error (epa)

$$epa(i+1) = i_{la}(i+1) - z_{pa}(i+1) \cdot h_{pa}(i) \quad (19)$$

2. Step size coefficient (β_{pa})

$$\beta_{pa}(i) = \frac{w R_{pa}^T(i) q_{pa}(i) + \theta_{pa}(i+1) R_{pa}^T(i) z_{pa}(i+1) epa(i+1)}{R_{pa}^T(i) x_{pa}(i) R_{pa}(i)} \quad (20)$$

3. Active weight vector (h_{pa})

$$h_{pa}(i+1) = h_{pa}(i) + \beta_{pa}(i) \cdot q_{pa}(i) \quad (21)$$

$$h_{pb}(i+1) = h_{pb}(i) + \beta_{pb}(i) \cdot q_{pb}(i) \quad (22)$$

$$h_{pc}(i+1) = h_{pc}(i) + \beta_{pc}(i) \cdot q_{pc}(i) \quad (23)$$

These equations perform the same adaptive update for active power weight vectors of phases 'b' and 'c', maintaining symmetry and learning dynamics for the whole system.

4. Reactive Weight Vectors (h_{qa})

$$h_{qa}(i+1) = h_{qa}(i) + \beta_{qa}(i) \cdot q_{qa}(i) \quad (24)$$

$$h_{qb}(i+1) = h_{qb}(i) + \beta_{qb}(i) \cdot q_{qb}(i) \quad (25)$$

$$h_{qc}(i+1) = h_{qc}(i) + \beta_{qc}(i) \cdot q_{qc}(i) \quad (26)$$

These update the reactive component weight vectors for all three phases similarly. These vectors model and compensate for reactive power in the system using CGA.

5. Average Weight

$$h_{p_{avg}} = \frac{h_{pa} + h_{pb} + h_{pc}}{3} \quad (27)$$

$$h_{q_{avg}} = \frac{h_{qa} + h_{qb} + h_{qc}}{3} \quad (28)$$

The average active and reactive weights across three phases are calculated to obtain a unified control signal. This average is used in the final current reference generation for balancing all phases.

6. Net Weight

$$h_{sp} = h_{p_{avg}} + h_{cp} - h_{pv} \quad (29)$$

This equation determines the net active weight used for current reference generation. It combines average active weights, controller part h_{cp} , and subtracts the PV feed forward weight h_{pv} to isolate the disturbance or compensation part.

7. PV Feed forward Weight

$$h_{pv} = \frac{2P_{pv}}{3v_t} \quad (30)$$

This calculates the PV feed forward signal based on available PV power and voltage normalization. It ensures the reference current considers real-time PV contribution to reduce grid dependency. This entire CGA structure helps dynamically generate reference currents for the APF system to maintain grid stability, minimize harmonics, and efficiently use PV energy. These currents are then used by the hysteresis controller to generate PWM signals that drive the VSC (Voltage Source Converter).

V. DC-DC Buck-Boost Converter for EV Charging strategy

The DC to DC buck boost converter is a power electronic circuit commonly used in electric vehicle charging systems to provide a regulated output voltage that may be either higher or lower than the input voltage. This is especially useful when the input supply from the grid or renewable energy sources such as solar or wind does not match the required charging voltage of the EV battery. The converter operates based on the duty cycle of the pulse width modulation control signal as shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8 bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter for EV charging

The mathematical relationship between the input and output voltage is given by the formula

$$V_{out} = \left(\frac{D}{1-D} \right) * V_{in} \quad (31)$$

where D is the duty cycle, Vin is the input voltage, and Vout is the output voltage.

In the ON state of the converter, the switch conducts current and allows the inductor to store energy from the input source. The inductor current during this period increases according to

$$\frac{diL}{dt} = \frac{V_{in}}{L} \quad (32)$$

where L is the inductance value. In the OFF state, the switch is open and the energy stored in the inductor is transferred to the output load through the freewheeling diode. During this phase, the inductor current changes as

$$\frac{diL}{dt} = \frac{V_{out}}{L} \quad (33)$$

The converter also includes an output capacitor that smoothes out voltage ripples to provide a constant DC output. The voltage ripple across the output capacitor can be estimated using

$$\Delta V_{out} = (I_{out} * D) / (f * C) \quad (34)$$

where Iout is the output current, f is the switching frequency, and C is the capacitance.

This type of converter supports both constant current and constant voltage charging strategies. Initially, when the state of charge of the battery is low, the converter operates in constant current mode by regulating the current flowing to the battery. As the state of charge increases and reaches around 80 percent, the converter switches to constant voltage mode, reducing the charging current to avoid overcharging. The control system of the buck boost converter typically uses proportional integral or intelligent control techniques to maintain the desired output voltage and current. Its ability to handle both step up and step down voltage

regulation makes the buck boost converter highly suitable for flexible and efficient electric vehicle charging.

VI. Bidirectional AC-DC Voltage Source Converter for EV Charging

The bidirectional AC-DC Voltage Source Converter (VSC) serves as the interface between the EV battery's DC link and the AC grid, enabling both Grid-to-Vehicle (G2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) power flow as shown in Fig.9. Its control architecture consists of an outer voltage loop that regulates the DC-link voltage Vdc and an inner current loop that controls the grid-side currents in the synchronous dq frame as shown in Fig.10.

Fig.9 grid connected bidirectional voltage source converter for EV charging

Fig. 10. VSC control and mode selection.

In the outer loop the DC-link voltage error

$$e_v(t) = (V_{dc}^* - V_{dc}(t)) \quad (35)$$

is fed to a PI controller

$$I_d^*(t) = K_{pV} e_v(t) + K_{iV} \int e_v(t) dt \quad (36)$$

Which generates the reference d-axis current Id*. The reference q-axis current is set to zero (Iq*=0) to enforce unity power factor during charging or discharging. In the inner current loop the actual grid currents Id and Iq,

obtained by Park transforming the three-phase measurements, are compared to their references. The resulting current errors drive separate PI regulators that produce the converter's dq-axis voltage references:

$$V_d^* = K_{pi}(I_d^* - I_d) + K_{ii} \int (I_d^* - I_d) dt + \omega L_c I_q + V_d \quad (37)$$

$$V_q^* = K_{pi}(I_q^* - I_q) + K_{ii} \int (I_q^* - I_q) dt + \omega L_c I_d + V_q \quad (38)$$

Here L_c is the converter filter inductance, ω is the grid angular frequency, and V_d, V_q are the grid voltage components in the dq frame, acting as feed forward terms to decouple the axes and improve dynamic response. These dq voltage references are then transformed back to three-phase signals via the inverse Park transformation and used by a PWM modulator to generate the gate pulses for the VSC switches. During G2V the converter draws a controlled I_d from the grid to charge the DC link, and during V2G it injects power back by reversing the current direction. The combined outer-inner loop structure ensures tight regulation of the battery voltage and fast rejection of grid disturbances while maintaining sinusoidal, balanced currents and near unity power factor.

VII. Simulation Results and Discussion

A. Impact of Operating Modes on Grid Current THD in Solar-Wind EV Charging System

The performance of the proposed bidirectional EV charging system integrated with solar and wind energy sources was analyzed under various operating conditions using MATLAB/Simulink. The system consists of a 27 kW solar PV system, a 20 kW wind power system, and a 20 kW EV battery. In the Grid to EV (G to EV) condition, where there is no power generation from solar and wind sources, the EV draws the full charging power directly from the grid. Under this mode, the grid current exhibits a Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) of 5.76%, primarily due to the complete reliance on grid power. When solar and wind power generation begins, the system enters the Renewable Energy Sources to EV and Grid (RES to EV & Grid) condition. In this scenario, the generated renewable energy first meets the EV charging demand, and any surplus power is exported to the grid. During this operation, the grid current THD is reduced to 5.51%, showing an improvement in power quality due to the integration of renewable sources. As the wind power contribution increases, the surplus renewable energy sent to the grid becomes more significant, further reducing grid dependency. This leads

to a further decrease in grid current THD to 3.4%, highlighting the positive impact of wind energy on power quality enhancement. In the case of EV to Grid (V2G) operation, where there is an emergency or total absence of solar and wind generation, the EV battery discharges back to the grid to support its load. In this mode, due to inverter-based energy injection, the grid current THD slightly increases to 6.37%. These results demonstrate that the system effectively manages power flow across different modes and that the integration of renewable energy sources, especially wind power, plays a critical role in reducing harmonic distortion and enhancing grid power quality.

Fig.11 Simulation Results under Different Renewable Power Variation Conditions

B. Dynamic Simulation Results and THD Performance Over Time

The proposed solar-wind integrated bidirectional EV charging system was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink for a total run time of 1 second, capturing multiple dynamic operating scenarios to evaluate power quality performance. During the initial 0 to 0.2 seconds, the system operates in the Grid to EV (G to EV) mode, where both solar and wind sources are inactive, and the EV

receives its full charging power (20 kW) directly from the grid. In this condition, the system experiences moderate harmonic distortion due to the absence of renewable support. From 0.2 to 0.4 seconds, the system switches to the EV to Grid (V2G) mode, where the EV discharges energy back to the grid during an emergency scenario with no renewable generation. This inverter-based back-feeding slightly increases harmonic distortion compared to the previous mode. After a brief transition, from 0.5 seconds onwards, solar power generation begins. The system now operates in the Renewable to EV and Grid (RES to EV & Grid) mode, where solar energy first satisfies the EV demand, and the excess is fed into the grid. This reduces the stress on the grid and improves power quality. Finally, from 0.7 to 1 second, wind power generation is added alongside solar, increasing the renewable share and further supporting the grid. As a result, the power quality significantly improves, marking this condition as the most stable among all. This highlights the effectiveness of the proposed system in adapting to dynamic energy flows and ensuring enhanced grid support and quality as shown in Fig.12. The results clearly demonstrate that the integration of solar and especially wind energy not only supports EV charging but also contributes to overall grid stability and harmonic mitigation.

Fig. 12 simulation results of dynamic power flow condition under Different Renewable Power Variation Conditions

The proposed solar-wind integrated bidirectional EV charging system was tested under various operating conditions to evaluate its impact on grid power quality. In the Grid to EV (G to EV) condition, where both solar and wind sources are inactive and the electric vehicle is charged directly from the grid, the grid current THD was observed to be 5.76%. In the EV to Grid (V2G) mode, where the EV battery discharges energy back to the grid due to the absence of renewable generation, the THD

increased to 6.37% as a result of inverter-based power injection. When only solar power is available and is used to supply both the EV and the grid, the THD reduces to 5.51%, indicating a moderate improvement in grid power quality. Further enhancement is seen when both solar and wind power are available and contribute to supplying the EV and exporting surplus energy to the grid. In this condition, the grid current THD significantly drops to 3.48%, reflecting the positive influence of increased renewable integration on harmonic reduction and overall system stability.

(a) Grid to EV

(b) EV to Grid

(c) Solar to EV and grid

(d) Solar and wind to grid and EV

Fig.13 THD Analysis under Various Operating Condition

VIII. Conclusion

This paper presented a novel approach for enhancing power quality in a solar-wind integrated grid system designed for bidirectional electric vehicle (EV) charging using a Conjugate Gradient Controller (CGC). The integration of renewable energy sources, particularly wind and solar, with the grid not only supports sustainable energy goals but also provides a robust and clean supply for EV charging infrastructure. The proposed bidirectional voltage source converter (VSC), governed by the CGC algorithm, demonstrated superior performance in regulating active and reactive power flow, improving system stability, and maintaining voltage and current waveforms within acceptable limits. Simulation results confirmed that the CGC effectively reduces Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and ensures compliance with IEEE-519 standards even under dynamic load and generation conditions as shown in Fig.13. Moreover, the controller's adaptive characteristics allow for rapid response to changing grid scenarios, maintaining power quality and enhancing the reliability of the entire charging process. The proposed system offers a promising solution for future smart grids by enabling high-quality, renewable-based, and bidirectional EV charging while preserving grid performance and supporting clean energy integration.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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